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Instructional Approach To Nigerian Musical Composition: A Study Of Some Nigerian Composers

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ABSTRACT

The Nigerian identity in musical compositions have been the driving force of several musicologists for a very long period of time. Composers such as Sowande, Euba, Uzoigwe, Ekwueme, Akpabot and several others have been studied to unearth their unique identities and the ‘Nigerianness’ their works are imbued with. However, several of these studies are not geared towards an instructional approach. While we have studied various compositional procedure and techniques of the Europeans a great deal, it is even more necessary to look deeper into the unfolding of our Nigerian art music. An instructional approach is necessary as it prepares a newer generation for more works that bears the Nigerian identity. This paper studies analytically, the works of Ndubuisi, Nwankpa, Onyeji, Adeogun and few others, digging out their various uniqueness, intricacies and compositional approaches as well as some Igbo folk songs as a means of instructing African art music composition. It is believed that this approach will serve as springboard for composers to dive into newer levels of creativity having drunk from the depth of master composers.

Keywords: Composers, musicologists, instructional approach

INTRODUCTION

Nigerian Identity as used in this paper refers to the unique approaches of Nigerian composers as asserted in their musical works. While many of their works were written for the human voice and accompanied by the European piano, they made immense efforts to apply African feel in their works. Some of the ways this was achieved was the use of unique African rhythms, employing some folk idioms, and introduction of creative figurations that simulates African dance patterns.

In folk melodies, several melodic organizational patterns have been discovered which can be used to create new folk-like melodies. The several patterns conform to a system of logogenic structure as evident in several African works. The words, emotions and cultural relevance guide the structuring of such melodies. Many of the melodies are short as written. But in performance, they are usually longer by means of repetition. During performance, some of the words are permuted to accommodate performance contingencies such as replacing a certain name with another as required. This may lead to some minor melodic alterations.

Theoretical framework

The concept Nigerian music, and indeed African music requires to be described firstly. Agawu (2003) describes African music as ‘those numerous repertoires of song and instrumental music that originate in specific African communities, are performed regularly as part of play, ritual, and worship, and circulate mostly orally/aurally, within and across language, ethnic, and cultural boundaries.’ Many Nigerian art

composers draw their compositions from indigenous music which is informed by indigenous cultural sensibility. Nwankpa (2015) once referred to African musical art as being “rooted in African indigenous knowledge system and practice.” (p.9).

Many of the analyses done in this work are based on rhythmic motion as Nigerian music is heavily characterized by rhythmic features. The creation, permutation, extension and truncation of a rhythmic figure or groups of figure shows compositional patterns which helps to create the form, melodic structure, vocal/instrumental parts/roles and general music expression. The centrality of rhythm in Nigerian art music expression also highlights the ethnomusicological backgrounds as well as the dance insinuations they imbue. Roger, (2002) also posited that:

Rhythm and percussion are highly emphasized in African music, reflecting the close link between music and dance. African music tends to feature complex polyrhythm; in which, several different rhythmic patterns are play simultaneously and repeated over and over, and each instrument goes its own rhythmic way.

Ofuani (2014) expressed similarly that rhythm is the nucleus of several Nigerian Art music genres borne out of ethnomusicological research:

And so, in referring to original Nigerian art music genres or styles, we hear and say African pianism, drummistic piano, native-air and African-vocalism etc. Quite often, I indulged in critical and analytical inquiry in order to ascertain the principal attribute of African music that supports and elicits the above indigenous art music genres/styles as distinct and original to African/Nigerian. The apt conclusion always settles to African rhythmic nuance.

Some composers have come up with recognizable rhythmic patterns borne from interaction with traditional music cum creative exploration. Referring to this, Ofuani (2014) described Okechukwu Ndubuisi’s rhythms thus:

The rhythms are of two types. He essentially applied a type in the right hand and the other in the left hand side of the piano accompaniment to his folksong arrangements. Base on harmonic sense, Njoku (1998: 244) refers to the left hand rhythmic type as Ndubuisi-bass.

But this paper in rhythmic sense refers to it as Ndubuisi-rhythms. (pp.167-168)

He further gave the rhythmic expression that characterizes many of his pieces as follows

Fig. 5. Ndubuisi right hand rhythmic pattern

Fig. 6. Ndubuisi left hand rhythmic pattern

Ofuani (2014, p.168)

Melodic organization and structures in Nigerian folk songs

Melodies take up several forms and structures based on the desire of the composer, the sonic tolerance of the culture involved, the function of the music and the performance media involved. However, some structures are given below regarding the melodic organization of some folk songs

1. **Sequential melody:** This is a melody based on repeated patterns at different tonal levels. The repetition may or may not be based on a particular word or phrase. It may end with a closing phrase or theme.

Allegro **ORIRI** An Igbo folk song

Lead singer

O-ri-ri, o-ri-ri, o-ri-ri no, o-ri-ri biam biam n'o-nu

Response

O-ri-ri biam biam n'o-nu

Ezi Nwa Na-Erube Isi

phrase 1 phrase 1 sequence phrase 1 modified sequence Closing theme

E-zi-gbo nwa na e - ru-be-re nne ya i-si, E-zi-gbo nwa e gi ru-be-re nne gi i - si.

(Okafor, 2017, p.166)

The encircled portions show the repeated notes. The last bar provides a cadential repose for the sequential journey before it. It also serves as a returning link for the repetition of the whole melody.

2. **Pivotal melody:** This is a kind of melody that reposes on a particular note. Many times, this note (or its repetition) serves as a cadential figure or a responsorial figure. The boxed part of the score below shows the note around which the phrases revolve.

Ihe Ebu Uzo Aju

I - h'e - bu - zo_a - ju n'e - be ni - le, i - h'e - b'u - zo_a - juo wu-nun - wa;

5
I - h'e - bu - zo_a - juo, i - h'e - b'u - zo_a - juo wu-nun - wa;

Okafor, 2017 (p.26)

In *Inine*, the boxed phrase serves as a unifying factor throughout the piece as well as a responsorial figure. In many folk tales, songs are in responsorial form, giving the audience an active participation in the story telling process. The score is given below:

Inine

An Igbo folk song

Oh! nwa mmuo ka m ko-ro gi, i - ni - ne. Nwu-nye_ dim_ di n-
 4 jo, i - ni - ne, e-je-rem ku-ru m-mi-ri m ge - nye nwa, i - ni - ne, o si mu
 7 kwuo y'u - gwo mmi-ri, mmi-ri nwa, i - ni - ne. M si ya echue m o - gba o si m'e-chu n'o-
 10 gba, i - ni - ne, ka-ma gi - ni, i - ni - ne, E-ze O - gba i - ni - ne, m-mi-ri
 13 se-re wam wam la n'e - lu i - gwe, i - ni - ne, m-mi-ri se-r'a mu-ma k'o- nwa n'e-
 16 ti i - ni - ne E - wo n - ne nwa'n - do I - ni - ne. E --
 19 wo n-ne nwa n - do i-ni-ne, do do do i - ni-ne do do do i - ni-ne

In *Ndo Keyi Wune Ndo*, as arranged by Okafor (2017) the pivotal figure didn't serve as a responsorial figure as found in *Inine*. The score is given below:

Ndo Keyi Wune Ndo

An Imezi-Owa Lullaby
Arranged by R.C.Okafor

N - do ke-yi wu-ne n-do, U-ne -je - wo - ge-ne, wa-ta - ki - li, Wa-ta - ki-
5 li n - ta u - la n'a - ta - ka, I n'a-kwa nu w'i - te m shi lu e-pe - hu, O pe-hu-kwe we
9 lu n-ke a - ka-ghu shi-kwu we, Wa ta m n'a - su-l'u-ta-la li-w'i-gbu-gbu, O-ji u-kpa a -
13 tu a-shi O-zo A ma-n - kwo, A-shim gu nu - l'o - gbu-gbo g'a-kw'a - naa n'a - kwa n -
17 hu i - n'a - kwa e - shi - e, N - do, u - ne m o

3. **Recycling phrases:** This refers to a group of rhythmic/melodic figure transferred to various pitches, not necessarily in a sequence, and could be altered at some points where the words demand so. It could have a foreign phrase as a contrasting part.

Nwa bu Ife Oma

The musical score for "Nwa bu Ife Oma" is presented in four systems, each with a treble clef and a key signature of one flat (Bb). The lyrics are written below the notes, and specific rhythmic patterns are labeled above the measures.

- System 1:** Measures 1-3. Labels: R1, R1(repeated), R1(repeated). Lyrics: "Na_nwa b'i-fe o- ma, na_nwa b'i fe o-ma. Na_nwa b'i-fe o- ma,"
- System 2:** Measures 4-6. Labels: R1(repeated), R2. Lyrics: "na_nwa b'i fe o-ma. O-nye Chu-kwu nye-lu ya na-lu ya na_nwa b'i-fe o- ma"
- System 3:** Measures 7-9. Labels: R1(modified), R1(modified), R1(modified). Lyrics: "Na_nwa bu_n-go-zi na_nwa bu_n-go-zi Na_nwa bu_n-go-zi"
- System 4:** Measures 10-12. Labels: R1(modified), R2, R1(modified). Lyrics: "na_nwa bu_n-go-zi O-nye Chu-kwu nye-lu ya na-lu ya na_nwa bu_n-go-zi"

(Okafor, 2017, p.30)

R1 (Rhythm 1)

R2 (Rhythm 2)

The introduction of R2 was a useful to create variety. The modification of R2 was pertinent to accommodate the way the term *ngozi*, it is pronounced naturally. This shows that African vocal composition pays so much respect to the words.

4. **Refrained-Consequent melody:** This is a melody with a repeated consequent whether it's antecedent gets altered or not. It appears as if it is a response or refrain to a call. However, in this case, the assumed call and response aren't shared by two or more parts but stated together to form a composite straight melody by one voice. This should not be confused with solo and piano arrangement where a voice is made to state both the call and response owing to the fact that there's no other available voice for sharing to take place.

Waya Mu Na Ehelu Wa

Wa-ya mu n'e - he lu wa e - me- gbuo-nu mu, O ye-ho mu du - l'a-chi-cha I -

he n-ku-ta n'e - li I - mi-li-ko a-n'e - kwe-ho mu me gbuo wa m n'e - he.

*modified refrained antecedent

(Okafor, 2017 p.57)

In the piece above, the first two bars provide the antecedent while the next two bars become the refrained consequent. This consequent is repeated in a modified form in bars 7 and 8 as a sequel to the antecedent in bars 5 and 6. Bars 9 and 10 provides an antecedent followed by the same refrained consequent in bars 11 and 12. Note that the refrained consequent is not necessarily set to the same words.

5. **Straight melody:** Here, the melody is stated without sequences and further repeated at same pitches (with or without permutations at points where new syllables and tonal inflections demand so.)

Obi Kererenke

An Igbo folk song

O - bi ke - re - re n - ke O - bi

O Ba Mamiri N'ute

O ba ma - mi - ri n'u - te, a - wo g'a - ta - bi - ri y'i - ke

(Okafor, 2017 p.142)

Types of accompaniment

Looking at the various composed or notated music of Nigerian composers, there are certain figurations evident in their works by way of accompaniment. Below are figurations found in some works of Nigerian composers.

1. **Arpeggio figuration:** This is the accompaniment arrived at when harmony provided is presented in the form of arpeggio (broken chord)

This is evident in Ndubuisi's *Nnam Fin So* (1987), bar 18. Here, the E-flat major 7th chord was given an arpeggio treatment in the piano accompaniment.

2. **Melody figuration:** This is the accompaniment governed by the notes and rhythm of the melody or the tune being accompanied. This use appears as chords, (usually block chords) lying below the melody they accompany. An example is given below in Adeogun's *Oniyangi (2002)*

In the excerpt below, the notes for *Epo ni mo ru* was duplicated as uppermost notes in the piano accompaniment.

In the 28th bar of *Uwa Iden Mi* by Ndubuisi, the melody is doubled in the accompaniment with the addition of other notes to create harmony and interest.

In *Abanije* as arranged by Kayode, O., the melody formed the basis of the accompaniment with addition of harmony.

Several works by same composer/arranger has similar examples.

3. **Accompaniment-response figuration:** This is a case whereby an accompaniment figure responds to a call made by the melody-bearing part or emphasizing the response usually in a solo-piano arrangement of a folk song. This is used to depict "call and response" style.

An example is given below in Ndubuisi's *Oma by nwunye mu o* in bar 4.

4. **Composer-style figuration:** This is an accompaniment figure or style that has unique features created by a particular composer or used by certain composers. A very good example is O’ndu bass used by Okechukwu Ndubuisi as shown in the works below: In *Uwa Idem Mi*, a unique figuration is used in the bass line. This has been shown with sections marked with rectangular blocks. This actually gives the music some kind of character.

UWA IDEM MI
(Ibibio Folksong)

Arr. Okechukwu Ndubuisi

Moderato Grazioso

U - wa'i - dem minam - die_ mio!

Moderato Grazioso

This figuration has been extensively used in various compositions as shown below: In *Onye nyere m aka?* an Nsukka folksong for high voice arranged by Adeogun (2006), the same figuration used by Ndubuisi was employed in bars 13 and 14.

I - we a bia o, i - we n'o - nu - ma

This can also be seen in bars 29 to 31 as shown below:

Nwa - m'e - sue o, i - we a

In *Atulegwu*, the same figure can be seen in the bass part of bars 7-10

A - tu - l'e - gwu gi kam_ non - ye - re

Take note of the use of 'melody figuration' on the treble staff which are basically block chords built beneath the melody being accompanied.

And also in bars 21-25

21. *bu, mi-o-wem bu, mu-o-wen bu,*

In *Ilesanmi* by Adeogun (2004), bars 65-67, the same figuration was also applied.

I-le-san-mi dun, o dun jo-ye

Apart from examples from Adeogun's works, Onyeji has also be found to utilized O'ndu's bass figuration. This is evident in *Giri giri* as shown below in bars 14.

The musical score consists of three staves. The top staff is a vocal line in treble clef with a key signature of one flat and a 6/8 time signature. It contains the lyrics "La - rin - ka ku n'i - le a k'o - ke r'o - ko". The middle and bottom staves are piano accompaniment in grand staff notation. The piano part features block chords in the right hand and a simple bass line in the left hand.

This is also evident in bars 28-30 and 32 of the same piece.

5. **Creative figuration:** In this case, the composer employs various established techniques at his disposal such as block chords, suitable melodies/ fragments of melodies, scale motions, sequences etc. or combination of any of them to accompany a tune.

Block chords are used in the piece as shown below as a creative means of harmonizing/accompanying the melody above it.

This musical score is identical to the one above, showing a vocal line and piano accompaniment in 6/8 time with the same lyrics: "La - rin - ka ku n'i - le a k'o - ke r'o - ko".

In the example below, Nwankwo, in his *Bata re adun Ko ko ka* used block chords but with some rhythmic interest which added to the aesthetics of the piece. Bars 30-31 have been extracted to support this idea.

A musical score in 4/4 time. The top staff is a vocal line with the lyrics "ba-ta re-a-dun, ba-ta-re-a-dun, ba-ta re-a-dun, ba-ta-re-a-dun,". The bottom two staves are piano accompaniment, featuring a rhythmic pattern of eighth and sixteenth notes in the right hand and a bass line in the left hand.

In Aina (1992) solo and piano accompaniment vocal piece, titled *Bi koko ba fe ni l'efe*, he creatively employed unique chordal motions and melodies which help to garnish the accompaniment.

A musical score in 8/8 time. The top staff is a vocal line with the lyrics "Bi 'ko ko_ ba fe 'ni l'e - fe n - ko!" and "to fe 'ni l'e - fe o!". The bottom two staves are piano accompaniment, featuring a complex rhythmic pattern of eighth and sixteenth notes in the right hand and a bass line in the left hand.

6. **Ethnomusicological figuration:** Here, a rhythmic or harmonic figure adopted from ethnomusicological research is applied as an accompaniment. In 'Agada Giri', Onyeji was inspired by the Ohafia war dance rhythm as given below:

This figure was repeatedly used in the accompaniment as shown below:

Voice

ka lan ko lo ti ti ko ko ko ti ti ti ti ko ko dam i-ya.

Piano

18

ulu

Voice

Pno.

Instructional Procedure

Having made the foregoing analytical studies on melody formation/structuring of Igbo folksongs cum accompaniment figurations derived from several Nigerian composers, let us follow the procedures below to create a new piece of music:

- Decide what you want to compose
- Decide the cultural background
- Decide the medium of composition
- Decide the form/design of the composition
- Decide the compositional materials to be employed

Let us follow the principles above to create a compositional structure

- What to compose: A vocal composition

- (b) Cultural background: A woman pleading that her only son should not be conscripted for tribal war.
- (c) Medium: Solo voice with piano accompaniment
- (d) Form/Design: Ternary form.

Time Signatures	12/8
Key Signatures	A major
Titles	OFU MKPURU ANYA
Bar Numbers	1 3 5 7 9 11 13 15 17 19 21 23
Voice	
Piano (a)	
Piano (b)	

However, this design can be adjusted if need be in the course of the composition.

- (e) Compositional materials: O’Ndu bass (OB), Melody-of-song figuration (MSF), Sequential melody (SF), Refrained consequent (RC). Pivotal melody (PM) and Arpeggio figuration (AP).

Below is a musical composition following the foregoing compositional procedures.

OFU MKPURU ANYA

Elueme, Lucky O.

Voice

Piano

MSF RC

Voice

Pno.

Sequences leading to the arrival of the vocal line

Voice

5 **A** SM.....

U-mu n-ze, U-mu n-ze, o bu kw'o-fu m-kpu-ru a-nya ji i-si u-gwo

Pno.

A MSF RC

2

7

Voice

A kpo la nwa mu jee a - gha o, bu kw'o-fu m-kpu-ru a-nya ji i-si u-gwo

MSF RC

Pno.

9

Voice

U-wa u-mu-nwa yi si-r'i-ke, a no-rom a-fi-ri, a-mu-ghi m n-wa,

CF

Pno.

11

Voice

n-ke mbu m-mu-ru da-ba-r'o-lu-lu, na-ni O-bi n-na fo-ro

CF

Pno.

13

Voice

MSF RC

Pno.

15

Voice

Pno.

Sequences leading to the arrival of the vocal line

17 **B**

Voice

O bu-ru n'O-bi n-na jee a - gh'a-hu, m-gbó g'a-tu ya n'i - si,

Pno.

B CF

19

Voice

u - be g'a-ma ya n'a-ku-ku, a - ri - ri g'e - ji - de mu gbuo.

Pno.

CF

21 **A** SM..... **RC**

Voice

U-mu n-ze, U-mu n-ze, o bu kw'o-fu m-kpu-ru a-nya ji i-si u-gwo

Pno.

A **RC**

4

23 **poco rit.** **RC**

Voice

A kpo la nwa mu jee a - gha o, O bu kw'o-fu m-kpu-ru a-nya ji i-si u-gwo

poco rit. **RC**

Pno.

KEY

MSF: Melody-of-song figuration

CF : Creative figuration

RC : Refrained Consequent

SM : Sequential melody

The reiteration of theme as refrained consequent creates a lasting impression on the listener. Much is not said about the left hand because it simply provided suitable notes that filled in as the foundation of the chords rather. However, it can perform more roles such as ostinato, pulse marking, responses etc.

Textual Analysis

The use of female voice is employed to fit the female role of the story the song captures. The use of *ofu mkpuru anya ji isi ugwo* as refrained consequent was based on the fact that it captures the general meaning of the song. *Ofu mkpuru anya ji isi ugwo* literally means *the single eye that owes blindness a debt*. It captures the woman's unwillingness to release her only son for battle which is the central idea of the song.

Translation

Igbo: Umunze, Umunze, O bu kwa ofu mkpuru anya ji isi ugwo

English: Umunze, Umunze, this is my only beloved and highly cherished child

Igbo: Akpola nwa mu jee agha o, O bu kwa ofu mkpuru anya ji isi ugwo

English: Please, don't conscript my child for war, this is my only beloved and highly cherished child.

Igbo: Uwa umu Nwanyi siri ike, anoro afo iri amughi m nwa, nke mbu m muru dabara olulu, nani Obinna foro

English: The life of women is a tough one. I couldn't conceive for ten years, the first child I had fell into a pit. Obinna is the only child left.

CONCLUSION

This paper successfully gives an instructional approach to composing Nigerian art music by drawing ideas from the analysis of master composers. This has led to the indepth analysis of the melodic and harmonic structures that is applied in several celebrated Nigerian Art compositions.

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